

A 21-Year Analysis of Students' Performance in West African Secondary School Certificate (WASSCE) Physics and Chemistry Examinations in Nigeria (1999-2019)

Deborah. T. A. Obafemi ✉

*Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria*

Rosemary C. Ugonwa ✉

*Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria*

Article History:

Received: 28.03.2025 Revised: 19.04.2025 Accepted: 23.04.2025 Published: 23.04.2025

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the performance of students in the West African Senior Secondary School Certificate Physics and Chemistry Examinations in Nigeria in the years 1999-2019. All the 19,753,590 students who sat for the examinations between 1999 and 2019 were involved in the study. The study adopted the Expo facto research design. The instrument for the study was the Summary of results of students in Physics and Chemistry Examinations obtained from the West African Examination Council, from which the data was gathered. The students' performance were analyzed using percentages, means, and correlation. These findings of the analysis revealed an unstable pattern in the performance of students in the two subjects. Only 51.78% and 50.84% of the students who enrolled for the WASSCE Physics and Chemistry respectively scored credits and above between 1999 and 2019. The study further revealed that though there was a slightly higher performance in WASSCE Physics examination than in WASSCE Chemistry examination, there was a significant positive and moderate correlation between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019. The study then recommends that all stakeholders work together to tackle all the weaknesses reported by the WAEC Chief examiners report, in which the lack of understanding of Physics and Chemistry concepts by the students is topmost.

Keywords: *Analysis, Students' Performance, Physics, Chemistry, Examination.*

Suggested citation: Obafemi, D.T.A, & Ugonwa, R.C. (2025). A 21-Year Analysis of Students' Performance in West African Secondary School Certificate (WASSCE) Physics and Chemistry Examinations in Nigeria (1999-2019). *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(2), 555-566. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(2\).46](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(2).46)

Introduction

Physics is a branch of science that focuses on the study of energy and its interactions with matter. It involves the systematic acquisition of

knowledge through observation, measurement, and experimentation, aiming to formulate universal laws that explain the phenomena under investigation (Ivowi, 1999). In Nigerian secondary schools, Physics is a key component

of the science curriculum. Its significance is underscored by the requirement for students to earn at least a credit pass in Physics in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) to gain admission into higher education programs where Physics knowledge is essential. This is due to the fundamental role Physics plays in understanding and applying technological concepts. The subject contributes extensively to technological progress through its theories, principles, and practical applications. Its relevance spans multiple sectors—including education, agriculture, engineering, ICT, medicine, manufacturing, and astronomy—making it a vital and engaging subject that connects theoretical learning with real-world applications across various facets of the economy (Ivowi, 1999).

Chemistry, likewise, is a foundational science subject taught at the secondary school level. It explores the composition, characteristics, and transformations of matter (Dike & Ugonwa, 2021). As one of the physical sciences, Chemistry is typically introduced as a distinct discipline, building on prior understanding of Physics, Biology, and Mathematics. Defined as the science concerned with the properties and structures of elements and compounds, Chemistry also examines how substances change states and the energy involved in these transformations (Ugonwa, Agbai & Osuji, 2014). It investigates the chemical elements and their interactions at the atomic and molecular levels, exploring their behaviors, reactions, and the principles governing those changes. Often described as the "central science," Chemistry is a critical discipline that supports advancements in science and technology. It also delves into chemical bonding and the nature of compounds. Chemists, as practitioners in this field, carry out experiments involving molecular substances, develop and refine chemical products, and evaluate chemical processes. Key specializations within Chemistry include areas such as biochemistry, analytical chemistry, and geochemistry (Ugonwa, Agbai & Osuji, 2014; Mukhtari, 2017).

Physics and Chemistry are both physical Sciences studied at the secondary school level. These two subjects deal with the study of matter,

though they are different in how they study it and what they focus on. While Chemistry studies what makes up matter, Physics studies matter and how matter interacts with energy. However, the study of Physics and Chemistry are related in that they have so many concepts in common. These concepts include concepts of matter, mass-volume relationships, energy, motion, kinetic theory, acid, bases and salts, heat and thermodynamics, Gas laws, Periodic table, metals and their compounds, electrolysis, chemical reactions, chemical bonding, molecular structure, atomic structure/atomic theory, quantum mechanics, nuclear energy, as well as mathematical and scientific methods. Students benefit from the study of Physics and Chemistry because of these common concepts, in such a way that if a student can grasp the understanding of a concept from either of the subjects, the student will be able to easily understand and relate with the same concept in the second subject.

Through the study of Physics and Chemistry, students are introduced to the scientific method and acquire vital skills such as critical thinking, analytical reasoning, effective problem-solving, and clear communication. These subjects also cultivate important scientific values, including open-mindedness, integrity, and the ability to withhold judgment until sufficient evidence is available. By engaging with these disciplines, learners gain a richer understanding of the natural world and are better equipped for diverse career paths and roles within science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. Additionally, Physics and Chemistry contribute significantly to the development of technologies and strategies that help us observe, safeguard, and enhance our environment—including the air we breathe and the water we use. They play a critical role in addressing key global challenges such as sustainable energy solutions, food security, environmental conservation, access to clean water, and the promotion of public and ecological health (LiveLaptopSpec, n.d.).

The practical impact of Physics and Chemistry is deeply woven into the fabric of our daily lives. From the moment we wake up to the time we go to bed—and even while we sleep—these

sciences influence our routines. They are responsible for innovations and products ranging from the food we consume to the air we inhale, and from personal hygiene products to medical treatments. Items like toothpaste, skincare products, soaps, pharmaceuticals, fabrics, and the batteries that power watches, mobile phones, laptops, and vehicles all exist thanks to the principles of Physics and Chemistry. These subjects also enable the functioning of everyday devices such as light bulbs, fans, and air conditioners, and contribute to fueling transportation. Their influence extends into virtually every aspect of modern human life (Ugonwa, Agbai & Osuji, 2014):

1. explaining natural phenomena such as lightning, earthquakes, and other chemical reactions in the environment.
2. informing the design and production of new materials and products.
3. playing a crucial role in the synthesis and development of new vaccines, medicines, and diagnostic tools.
4. helping us understand and mitigate the impact of human activities on the environment such as erosion, pollution, and climate change.
5. ensuring food security through agriculture.

The West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) is administered by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) (Ghana Education, 2023). This examination is a compulsory assessment for students who have completed the full six-year secondary education program in Nigeria. It serves both as a certification process and as a key qualification for entry into tertiary institutions within the country, enabling students to pursue various academic and professional pathways. The examination encompasses all subjects taught in Nigerian secondary schools, grouped under several academic and vocational disciplines. According to WAEC (2023), these subject categories include Civil and Mechanical Trades, Mathematics and Applied Sciences, Languages, Pure Sciences, Business Studies, Home Economics, and General Studies (NYSCinfo, n.d.).

In WASSCE Physics and Chemistry examinations, as outlined in multiple WAEC Chief Examiners' reports over the years, students are assessed across a broad spectrum of competencies (Jamal, & Setiawan, 2020). These include recalling and defining scientific facts, explaining and understanding principles, laws, and theories, and applying scientific terminology and conventions accurately. Students are also tested on their ability to interpret phenomena, apply basic scientific principles to real-life contexts, and demonstrate proficiency in practical skills. This includes conducting experiments, outlining experimental steps, solving quantitative problems, analyzing and interpreting data, drawing logical conclusions, and accurately documenting experimental results.

In their analysis of student performance in WASSCE subjects, Zalmon and Wonu (2017) conducted a study comparing mathematics achievement among Nigerian students. They observed a notable improvement in the percentage of students attaining credit passes and above in General Mathematics in the May/June WASSCE from 1991 to 2016. However, despite this progress, overall performance in mathematics during the 26-year period remained relatively poor. In a similar vein, Olarewaju et al. (2019), in their comparative analysis of students' achievement in Further Mathematics across Kwara State (2007–2016), reported that only about half of the students who took the WASSCE and NECO SSCE earned credit-level passes (A1–C6), with respective percentages of 51.37% and 50.92%.

Further evidence from Nweke et al. (2021), who examined Physics performance trends in the WASSCE across the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria between 2015 and 2017, revealed that in each of those years, the average percentage of students achieving high-grade passes in Physics exceeded 50%.

When examining year-by-year performance patterns, Jegede et al. (2013) discovered a fluctuating trend in Physics results among secondary school students in Ekiti State between 2007 and 2012. Similarly, Onudibia et al. (2019), in their study focusing on final-year students in

Zaria, noted an inconsistent pattern in student performance in both Physics and Chemistry. Supporting this, Olarewaju et al. (2019) found variable trends in Further Mathematics achievement, with student outcomes showing both increases and declines over the period analyzed.

Exploring the connection between achievement in Physics and Chemistry, Onudibia et al. (2019) observed that students tended to perform slightly better in Physics than in Chemistry, yet the correlation between their performances in both subjects was statistically significant. Additionally, Taangahar et al. (2021) found a positive relationship between student results in Physics and Mathematics in the WASSCE conducted in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, between 2015 and 2019.

Most students who offer Physics also offer Chemistry due to the requirements for admission into their desired courses of study in the higher institution, hence the similar number in enrolment for the two subjects in WASSCE over the years. Both Chemistry and Physics have however been perceived to be abstract, difficult, and complex in nature, and this has been attributed to various factors. These factors include the abstract nature of concepts, the mathematical nature of most of the concepts, as well as wide and overloaded curriculum. Other challenges facing the effective teaching and learning of the two subjects include teacher factors such as teacher's attitude/personality, instructional strategies, availability of laboratory, instructional materials, and facilities needed. Numerous reports have indicated that students have consistently underperformed in both Physics and Chemistry, not only in internal school assessments but also in national standardized examinations like the WASSCE. This raises important questions: Are students genuinely struggling with these subjects? And what is the nature of the relationship between students' achievements in WASSCE Physics and Chemistry from 1999 to 2019? In response to these concerns, this study examines the trends in student performance in WASSCE Physics and Chemistry over the two-decade period to either confirm or refute these observations.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to analyze the performance of students in WASSCE Physics and Chemistry between 1999 and 2019. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. investigate the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics between 1999 and 2019.
2. ascertain the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019.
3. determine the relationship between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the analyses:

1. What is the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics between 1999 and 2019?
2. What is the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019?
3. What is the relationship between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was tested in the analyses:

1. There is no significant relationship between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019.

Methodology

This study examined the academic performance of Nigerian students in WASSCE Physics and Chemistry from 1999 to 2019. An ex post facto research design was employed for the

investigation. The research utilized a census sampling method, incorporating all 9,831,543 candidates who took Physics and all 9,922,047 who took Chemistry in the WASSCE during the specified period, resulting in a combined sample size of 19,753,590 students (Eze, & Agi, 2021; Iji, & Harbor-Peters, 2016). The study relied on secondary data, specifically the compiled summaries of student results for both subjects, sourced from the West African Examinations Council (WAEC). Data analysis involved the use

of percentages, mean scores, and the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation technique (Onu, & Amadi, 2021; Ogunlade, & Akingbade, 2022).

Results and Findings

Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics between 1999 and 2019?

Table 1. Performance of Students in WASSCE Physics Based on Enrolment between 1999 and 2019

Year	Enrolment	No. of students who scored Credits & Above (A1-C6)	% of students who scored Credits & Above (A1-C6)
1999	210,271	64283	30.57
2000	195,226	38086	19.51
2001	298,513	101252	33.92
2002	335,388	157174	46.86
2003	305,442	143272	46.91
2004	321,499	158777	49.39
2005	344,411	142943	41.50
2006	375,823	218198	58.06
2007	418,593	180797	43.19
2008	415,108	200345	48.26
2009	465,636	222722	47.83
2010	463,755	237,756	51.27
2011	563,161	360,096	63.94
2012	624,658	429,415	68.74
2013	637,023	297,988	46.78
2014	635,729	386,270	60.76
2015	684,124	410,543	60.01
2016	705,125	415,655	58.95
2017	377,851	205,757	54.45
2018	728,354	571,687	78.49
2019	725,853	565,746	77.94

Source: Test Development Division, West African Examination Council (WAEC) Lagos, Nigeria.

Table 1 shows the yearly performance of students based on the enrolment for WASSCE Physics between 1999 and 2019. Between the years 1999 and 2009, the percentage of students who scored credits and above in Physics was lower than 50% except in the year 2006 which witnessed 58.06%. The year 2010 witnessed a positive turn of events as the number of students who scored credits and above jumped to 51.27%, and rose to 77.94% in the year 2019,

except in the year 2013 in which only 46.78% of students scored credits and above. In the 21 years under review, the year 2019 witnessed 77.97%, the highest percentage of students who scored credits and above, while the year 2000 witnessed the poorest percentage of 19.51%.

Research Question 2: What is the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019?

Table 2. Performance of Students in WASSCE Chemistry Based on Enrolment between 1999 and 2019

Year	Enrolment	No. of students who scored Credits & Above (A1-C6)	% of students who scored Credits & Above (A1-C6)
1999	223,305	69411	31.08
2000	202,900	64284	31.68
2001	312,946	111843	35.74
2002	348,291	119049	34.18
2003	313,330	154912	49.44
2004	327,503	124009	37.87
2005	349,936	178274	50.95
2006	380,103	170669	44.90
2007	422,681	194284	45.97
2008	418,423	185949	44.44
2009	468,546	204725	43.69
2010	465,643	236059	50.70
2011	565,692	280250	49.54
2012	627,301	270570	43.13
2013	639,296	462517	72.35
2014	636,268	397649	62.50
2015	680,357	412323	60.60
2016	706,873	408122	57.74
2017	377,970	320635	84.83
2018	728,551	424231	58.23
2019	726,132	566156	77.97

Source: Test Development Division, West African Examination Council (WAEC) Lagos, Nigeria.

Table 2 shows the yearly performance of students based on the enrolment for WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019. Between the years 1999 and 2009, the percentage of students who scored credits and above in Chemistry was lower than 50% except the year 2005 that witnessed 50.95%. The year 2010 witnessed a positive turn of events as the number of students who scored credits and above jumped to 50.70%, and rose to 77.97% in the year 2019, except in the years 2011 and 2012 in which only 49.54% and 43.13% of students scored credits

and above respectively. In the 21 years under review, the year 2019 witnessed 77.97%, the highest percentage of students who scored credits and above, while the year 1999 witnessed the poorest percentage of 31.08%.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019?

Table 3. Performance of Students in WASSCE Physics and Chemistry Based on Enrolment between 1999 and 2019

Year	Physics	Chemistry
	% of students who scored Credits & Above (A1-C6)	% of students who scored Credits & Above (A1-C6)
1999	30.57	31.08
2000	19.51	31.68
2001	33.92	35.74
2002	46.86	34.18
2003	46.91	49.44
2004	49.39	37.87
2005	41.50	50.95
2006	58.06	44.90

2007	43.19	45.97
2008	48.26	44.44
2009	47.83	43.69
2010	51.27	50.70
2011	63.94	49.54
2012	68.74	43.13
2013	46.77	72.35
2014	60.76	62.50
2015	60.01	60.60
2016	58.95	57.74
2017	54.45	84.83
2018	78.49	58.23
2019	77.94	77.97
Mean %	51.78	50.84

Source: Researchers

Table 3 shows that in eleven (11) of the 21 years, less than 50% of the students who sat for the WASSCE Physics in Nigeria scored credits in the subject, while in ten (10) of the 21 years, more than 50% of the students who sat for the WASSCE Physics in Nigeria scored credits in the subject. In twelve (12) of the 21 years, less than 50% of the students who sat for the WASSCE Chemistry in Nigeria scored credits in the subject, while in nine (9) of the 21 years, more than 50% of the students who sat for the

WASSCE Chemistry in Nigeria scored credits in the subject. Table 3 further shows that the mean percentage of students who scored credits in WASSCE Physics between 1999 and 2019 is 51.78%, while the mean percentage of students who scored credits in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019 is 50.84%. Figure 1 similarly shows the graphical illustration of the percentage of students who scored credits in WASSCE Physics and Chemistry between 1999 and 2019 in Nigeria.

Figure 1. Chart Showing the Percentage of Students Who Scored Credits in WASSCE Physics and Chemistry between 1999 and 2019 in Nigeria

Table 4. Correlation between the Performance of Students in WASSCE Physics and Chemistry between 1999 and 2019

Paired Samples Correlations		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	PHYSICS & CHEMISTRY	21	0.578	0.006

Table 4 shows the value of 0.578 for the correlation between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019. This result indicates a positive moderate correlation between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019.

Table 4 shows the value of $p = 0.006$ ($p < 0.05$) for the correlation between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019. This result indicates a significant relationship between the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Physics and the percentage of students who scored credits and above in WASSCE Chemistry between 1999 and 2019.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study indicate that among the 21 years reviewed, the lowest percentage of students achieving credit passes or higher in Physics occurred in 2000, while Chemistry recorded its lowest in 1999. Conversely, the highest percentage of credit-level performance in both subjects was seen in 2019, signaling a gradual improvement in students' outcomes over time. This positive trend might be attributed to ongoing educational reforms, enhanced curriculum design, increased adoption

of student-centered teaching methods, and greater commitment from learners themselves.

Further analysis revealed that the average percentage of students who attained credit passes and above in WASSCE Physics from 1999 to 2019 was 51.78%, while Chemistry saw a mean of 50.84%. These figures suggest that only about half of the examinees succeeded in reaching the credit benchmark. Despite a general upward trend, these scores remain suboptimal. One possible explanation for this is the recurring deficiencies highlighted in WAEC Chief Examiner reports for both subjects. These findings are consistent with those of Zalmon and Wonu (2017), who noted a modest improvement in mathematics results over a 26-year span, despite overall low performance. Similar trends were observed by Olarewaju et al. (2019), who found that just over half of the students who took WASSCE and NECO SSCE from 2007 to 2016 achieved credit passes (A1–C6), with mean rates of 51.37% and 50.92%, respectively. Likewise, Nweke et al. (2021) reported that in the South-east region of Nigeria between 2015 and 2017, over half the students scored high-grade passes in WASSCE Physics.

This study also found that, on average, student performance in Physics slightly exceeded that in Chemistry over the two-decade period, aligning with the findings of Onudibia et al. (2019), who reported a similar pattern. However, the data also highlighted notable fluctuations in performance in both subjects, reflecting inconsistencies that may again stem from the various shortcomings identified in Chief Examiner reports. These results support those of Jegede et al. (2013), who documented variable trends in Physics performance in Ekiti State, as well as those of Onudibia et al. (2019) and Olarewaju et al. (2019), who identified non-uniform trends in student outcomes in Physics,

Chemistry, and Further Mathematics, respectively.

Additionally, a moderate yet statistically significant positive correlation was found between the percentages of students who achieved credit passes or higher in Physics and Chemistry during the period studied. This relationship may be due to conceptual overlaps between the two subjects, which enable students to leverage knowledge in one to enhance their understanding of the other. These findings reinforce those of Onudibia et al. (2019), who also identified a meaningful link between performance in Physics and Chemistry, as well as Taangahar et al. (2021), who noted a positive correlation between students' Physics and Mathematics results in WASSCE.

Moreover, several recurring weaknesses have been identified among WASSCE candidates in both Physics and Chemistry, as outlined by the WAEC Chief Examiner, which may contribute to the persistent challenges in achieving higher performance levels:

1. Poor understanding of the language of communication hence the students could not understand the demands of some questions neither could they express themselves in clear and comprehensive language.
2. Inability to adhere to and carry out instructions logically and in sequence as demanded by the questions.
3. Shallow understanding of concepts.
4. Inability to correctly define basic terms and state laws with the conditions for which such laws hold.
5. Inability to correctly arrange a simple experimental set-up.
6. Inability to describe experimental procedures systematically.
7. Unfamiliarity with the measuring instruments used, evidenced by the students' inability to record data correctly to the required number of decimal places or significant figures.
8. Poor mathematical skills such as inability to solve numerical problems, arithmetic errors

and omissions of steps, application of wrong units, and omission of units.

9. Poor reportage of experimental findings.
10. Poor terminologies.
11. Bad handwriting.
12. Spelling mistakes.
13. Inability to balance equations.
14. Inability of students to handle numerical processes properly. These processes include:
 - a. Inability to choose the appropriate scale for plotting graphs
 - b. Recording of data correctly to the required number of decimal places.
 - c. Plotting acceptable graphs using fractions and decimal values.
 - d. Making reasonable and correct deductions from graphs.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate a pattern of inconsistency in students' achievement in both Physics and Chemistry over the years. While student performance was commendable in certain years, it was significantly below average in others. Such fluctuations pose a serious challenge to students who aim to pursue STEM-related careers, as unstable academic outcomes can limit their opportunities. To address this issue, it is essential for all relevant stakeholders to collaborate and tackle the recurring challenges highlighted in the WAEC Chief Examiner's reports—foremost among them being students' limited grasp of fundamental concepts in Physics and Chemistry.

Improving instruction in these subjects calls for teaching methods that incorporate relatable, contextualized examples and analogies drawn from students' everyday environments. This approach will help simplify complex scientific ideas and make them more accessible. Furthermore, hands-on laboratory activities should be made a mandatory component of Physics and Chemistry education. Such experiential learning gives students the chance to explore scientific principles independently, reinforcing their conceptual understanding.

Given the critical role that Physics and Chemistry play in national development, especially in the realm of science and technology, the erratic performance of students in these subjects is a pressing concern. It demands swift and practical interventions from educators, policymakers, and all other stakeholders to support the nation's scientific and technological growth.

Recommendations

Consequent on the findings of this analysis, the following recommendations were made:

1. Students should be encouraged to pay more attention to the study of English language to be able to understand the demands of the questions and also be able to express themselves in clear and comprehensive language.
2. Laboratory work should be made a compulsory and integral part of the physics lessons to expose the students to practical work from the early stages of their senior secondary education. They should be encouraged to independently try their hands on many class experiments before the examination.
3. Students should be given a solid background in mathematics to improve their handling of arithmetical processes.
4. Students should be encouraged to practice the handling of numerical processes and plotting of graphs as these are necessary components of the physics practical examination.
5. Physics and Chemistry teachers should endeavour to use familiar, local, and relevant examples and analogies to bring down physics concepts to the level of understanding of the students.
6. Efforts should be made by Physics and Chemistry teachers to ensure that the syllabus is covered within the years of senior secondary school education before the commencement of WASSCE.
7. Physics and Chemistry teachers should embrace modern teaching methods, strategies, and technology.

8. Government should encourage the teaching and learning of Physics and Chemistry by

- a. Employing qualified and well-trained teachers to teach Physics and Chemistry in Secondary schools.
- b. Providing well-equipped laboratories in schools.
- c. Providing encouragement for teachers through in-service training, incentives, etc.
- d. Encouraging teachers to write good textbooks that will help to reduce the difficulty of students in understanding physics concepts.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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